

**EFFICIENCY OF THE ELECTRONIC STEAM KIT FOR ARITHMETIC INSTRUCTION AND
 CHILDHOOD NEUROCOGNITIVE PERFORMANCE IN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS.**

**Diagnostic Assessment Instrument “TEST” on Knowledge, Skills, and
 Abilities in Arithmetic**

Instructions

1. Read each statement carefully.
2. Mark with an 'X' the option that best describes your level of agreement with the statement.

1: Never 2: Rarely 3: Sometimes 4: Frequently 5: Always

Section 1: Location of the Educational Institution

Question	Answer	
Is the educational institution located in an urban or rural area?	Urban	Rural

Section 2: Assessment of Knowledge and Skills in Arithmetic

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	I can perform simple addition of two-digit numbers without assistance.					
2	I understand the concept of subtraction and can solve basic problems involving it.					
3	I can recognize numerical patterns in sequences (e.g., 2, 4, 6, 8).					
4	I know how to use multiplication to solve simple real-life problems.					
5	I can divide objects or numbers into equal parts and understand the concept of division.					
6	I am able to identify which operation (addition, subtraction, multiplication, or division) I should use.					
7	I understand the relationship between even and odd numbers and can identify them.					
8	I can solve mathematical problems that involve more than one operation (e.g., addition and subtraction).					
9	I use strategies such as counting on my fingers or drawing to solve mathematical problems.					
10	I feel confident explaining how I solved a mathematical problem.					

SECTION 3: APPLICATION OF MATHEMATICAL KNOWLEDGE

3.1 Solve the following problem:

A farmer has 36 apples and wants to distribute them equally among 4 baskets. How many apples should go in each basket?

Answer: _____

3.2 If Pedro has 15 candies and gives away 7, how many does he have left?

Answer: _____

3.3 Complete the sequence:

3, 6, 9, ____, ____, ____

Answer: _____

SECTION 4: ACCESS TO TECHNOLOGY AND USE OF DIGITAL RESOURCES

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5
1	I have access to a computer or tablet to learn mathematics.					
2	I use digital applications or programs to practice mathematics.					
3	I have used a STEAM kit or electronic devices to learn mathematics.					
4	My school has digital resources for teaching mathematics.					
5	I enjoy learning mathematics with technology.					

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION